

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

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SBRT in lung cancer treatment

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Introduction: The data from the lung cancer studies worldwide have shown that SBRT can be established as the treatment of choice in non-operable stage I NSCLC with 2 year PF of 70%, OS of around 90%, and grade 3 late toxicity of less than 6%. The optimal fractionation regimen, as well as patient selection, remains controversial.

Aim: To present single center experience in SBRT of primary NSCLC

Material and methods: In institute for oncology and radiology of Serbia SBRT is performed in 6 selected patients with NSCLC with a total dose of 40Gy in 5 fractions, every other day, by using Rapid Arc technique. The patients were selected as non-suitable for surgery, conventional irradiation or SABR due to patient or tumor features (defined as complex according to ASTRO). ESTRO-ACROP guidelines for target volume delineation, RTOG 0813 dose constraints to OAR and treatment delivery were followed.

Results: In all our treated patients GPR or CR was observed with long term follow up. No radiation induced toxicity of any kind was observed.

Conclusion: With adequate patient selection and dose/fractionation regimen, SBRT can be safely administered with great response and minimal toxicity.

Keywords: SBRT, lung cancer, toxicity

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